

Adsorption of Sodium Oleate as Surfactant at the Interfacial Surface in Methyl-substituted-benzene – Water Emulsions

S. SHARAN SINGH* and N. NATH PANDEY

Department of Chemistry, Bhagalpur University, Bhagalpur-812 007

and

R. PRATAP SINGH

Department of Chemistry, Bhagalpur College of Engineering, Bhagalpur

Manuscript received 5 September 1988, revised 17 March 1989, accepted 7 June 1989

Adsorption of sodium oleate as surfactant on dispersed droplets in methyl-substituted-benzene – water emulsions has been studied. The amount a of the surfactant adsorbed per cm^2 of the droplet surface area at the corresponding equilibrium surfactant concentration C_s in the aqueous serum has been calculated in each case. The adsorption of the surfactant on the droplet surface does not saturate even if the $C_s > \text{CMC-III}$. The area σ_B corresponding to the adsorption of one oleate ion on the emulsion droplet surface and the molar adsorption energy E_{ad} have been calculated using a three-parameter modified BET equation and the data analysed. A comparison of E_{ad} for benzene – water – sodium oleate emulsion with that for methyl-substituted-benzene – water – sodium oleate emulsions led to an understanding of the nature of adsorption sites on the drop surface of the emulsions studied.

IN a previous communication¹, the authors described the adsorption of sodium oleate as surfactant on dispersed droplets in benzene – water emulsions. Extending the same work, it was considered worthwhile to study the effect of methyl-substituted-benzenes as disperse phase on the adsorption characteristics of sodium oleate as surfactant. In view of this, the present paper deals with the determination of the amount of surfactant adsorbed per cm^2 of the droplet surface area at the corresponding equilibrium surfactant concentration, the area corresponding to the adsorption of an oleate ion on droplet surface, the molar energy of adsorption and the number of adsorbed surfactant layers along with their variations with the nature of the dispersed phase.

Experimental

Toluene (B.D.H.) was used as disperse phase and sodium oleate (B.D.H.) as surfactant, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-xylenes (E. Merck) were used as disperse phases. The continuous phase in each case was double-distilled conductivity water having specific conductance $10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$ at 30° . Toluene and the xylenes were purified^{2,3} before use and their purity was checked by measuring their density and refractive index which compared well with the literature⁴ values. Sodium oleate was purified as described earlier¹.

Different methyl-substituted-benzene – water – sodium oleate emulsions of desired phase-volume

ratio (ϕ) were prepared by stirring methyl-substituted-benzene (as disperse phase) and aqueous sodium oleate solution of known concentration C (as dispersing phase) using a high speed mechanical stirrer at $30^\circ (\pm 0.1^\circ)$. The detailed procedures have been described elsewhere¹.

The specific conductivity (K_s) of the aqueous serum obtained after complete creaming of an emulsion as prepared above, was measured by using a Toshniwal CL01/01A conductivity bridge with a dipping cell with cell constant 1.1 and adopting the standard procedure with required precautions⁵. The sodium oleate concentration (C_s) in the serum was then obtained by interpolation of a K_s – C calibration curve. The conductometric method^{6,7} was highly sensitive for such work.

The emulsion droplet radii (r) were measured using a Censico TN-I-phot-35 mm microscope having Hertel and Reuss (West German) achromatic objective 100X and paired huyghenian eyepiece 15X. The details of the slide preparation, the experimental techniques and the determination of the droplet radius have been described in our earlier work¹. The average droplet radius (\bar{r}) was determined from the histogram plot using the measured radii of at least 200 droplets in each case.

Repeated determinations of the reported quantities led to an estimation of the uncertainties which did not exceed $\pm 0.00001 \text{ g}$ for weighings, ± 0.00001

mol dm⁻³ for C_s as obtained by K_s-C calibration curves, ± 2% for K_s and ± 0.01 μ for \bar{r} .

sodium oleate emulsions with different ϕ and C. The values of C_s in all cases are greater than the third critical micelle concentration* (CMC-III) ~ 2.1 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ for aqueous sodium oleate solution. This indicates that unlike the adsorption of surfactants on solid adsorbents in aqueous suspensions, the adsorption of sodium oleate on

Results and Discussion

Tables 1-4 include the experimental values of K_s, \bar{r} and C_s for methyl-substituted-benzene-water-

TABLE 1-ADSORPTION ISOTHERM DATA FOR TOLUENE/WATER EMULSIONS WITH SODIUM OLEATE AS SURFACTANT AT 30 ± 0.1°

C × 10 ⁴ mol dm ⁻³	\bar{r} μ	K _s × 10 ⁶ Ω ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	C _s × 10 ⁴ mol dm ⁻³	a × 10 ⁹ mol cm ⁻³	C × 10 ⁴ mol dm ⁻³	\bar{r} μ	K _s × 10 ⁶ Ω ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	C _s × 10 ⁴ mol dm ⁻³	a × 10 ⁹ mol cm ⁻³
$\phi = 0.30$					$\phi = 0.35$				
328.5	2.8	853.0	270.5	1.263	328.5	3.0	830.0	261.9	1.237
410.6	2.6	1 098.0	334.5	1.539	410.6	2.8	1 053.0	323.3	1.513
492.7	2.5	1 214.5	399.2	1.818	492.7	2.7	1 200.0	384.0	1.817
574.8	2.5	1 252.5	451.1	2.405	574.8	2.6	1 244.0	436.1	2.232
656.9	2.5	1 350.0	500.7	3.037	656.9	2.5	1 296.0	477.3	2.780
$\phi = 0.40$					$\phi = 0.45$				
328.5	3.0	792.0	247.0	1.223	328.5	3.2	773.0	235.9	1.207
410.6	2.9	1 016.0	313.2	1.412	410.6	3.0	939.0	297.9	1.379
492.7	2.8	1 188.0	375.5	1.641	492.7	3.0	1 155.0	358.8	1.637
574.8	2.7	1 229.5	423.9	2.037	574.8	2.9	1 223.0	409.3	1.955
656.9	2.6	1 265.0	464.0	2.508	656.9	2.8	1 253.0	451.5	2.343
$\phi = 0.50$					$\phi = 0.55$				
328.5	3.3	747.0	230.5	1.078	328.5	3.4	730.0	224.7	0.963
410.6	3.2	916.0	296.8	1.214	410.6	3.3	907.0	285.1	1.130
492.7	3.1	1 120.0	348.3	1.492	492.7	3.2	1 102.0	336.2	1.366
574.8	3.0	1 216.0	399.8	1.750	574.8	3.1	1 201.0	386.7	1.590
656.9	2.9	1 247.5	440.5	2.092	656.9	3.0	1 231.0	425.1	1.897
$\phi = 0.60$									
328.5	3.5	695.0	210.7	0.916					
410.6	3.4	839.0	265.2	1.099					
492.7	3.3	1 034.0	317.9	1.282					
574.8	3.2	1 163.0	363.3	1.504					
656.9	3.1	1 219.0	403.1	1.748					

TABLE 2-ADSORPTION ISOTHERM DATA FOR o-XYLENE/WATER EMULSIONS WITH SODIUM OLEATE AS SURFACTANT AT 30 ± 0.1°

C × 10 ⁴ mol dm ⁻³	\bar{r} μ	K _s × 10 ⁶ Ω ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	C _s × 10 ⁴ mol dm ⁻³	a × 10 ⁹ mol cm ⁻³	C × 10 ⁴ mol dm ⁻³	\bar{r} μ	K _s × 10 ⁶ Ω ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	C _s × 10 ⁴ mol dm ⁻³	a × 10 ⁹ mol cm ⁻³
$\phi = 0.30$					$\phi = 0.35$				
328.5	2.8	855.0	271.4	1.244	328.5	3.0	829.0	261.5	1.244
410.6	2.6	1 097.0	334.2	1.545	410.6	2.8	1 052.0	323.0	1.518
492.7	2.5	1 214.0	398.8	1.828	492.7	2.7	1 199.0	383.1	1.832
574.8	2.5	1 251.0	450.0	2.427	574.8	2.6	1 242.5	435.4	2.244
656.9	2.5	1 346.5	500.0	3.051	656.9	2.5	1 295.0	476.9	2.786
$\phi = 0.40$					$\phi = 0.45$				
328.5	3.0	806.0	251.2	1.160	328.5	3.2	777.5	239.7	1.158
410.6	2.9	1 017.0	313.3	1.411	410.6	3.0	940.0	298.0	1.376
492.7	2.8	1 186.0	375.0	1.648	492.7	3.0	1 153.0	358.2	1.644
574.8	2.7	1 229.0	423.3	2.045	574.8	2.9	1 222.0	409.1	1.958
656.9	2.6	1 263.5	446.3	2.517	656.9	2.8	1 252.0	450.9	2.350
$\phi = 0.50$					$\phi = 0.55$				
328.5	3.3	746.0	230.0	1.084	328.5	3.4	728.0	224.4	0.965
410.6	3.2	923.0	290.2	1.284	410.6	3.3	893.0	282.2	1.156
492.7	3.1	1 118.0	348.1	1.494	492.7	3.2	1 101.0	335.6	1.371
574.8	3.0	1 214.0	393.7	1.761	574.8	3.1	1 201.0	386.7	1.590
656.9	2.9	1 245.0	439.7	2.100	656.9	3.0	1 230.5	424.4	1.902
$\phi = 0.60$									
328.5	3.5	692.0	210.0	0.922					
410.6	3.4	838.0	265.0	1.100					
492.7	3.3	1 030.0	317.5	1.285					
574.8	3.2	1 161.0	362.6	1.509					
656.9	3.1	1 218.0	402.5	1.753					

TABLE 3 - ADSORPTION ISOTHERM DATA FOR *m*-XYLENE/WATER EMULSIONS WITH SODIUM OLEATE AS SURFACTANT AT $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$

$C \times 10^4$ mol dm ⁻³	\bar{r} μ	$K_s \times 10^6$ $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$C_s \times 10^4$ mol dm ⁻³	$a \times 10^6$ mol cm ⁻²	$C \times 10^4$ mol dm ⁻³	\bar{r} μ	$K_s \times 10^6$ $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$C_s \times 10^4$ mol dm ⁻³	$a \times 10^6$ mol cm ⁻²
$\phi = 0.30$					$\phi = 0.35$				
328.5	2.8	852.0	270.0	1.274	328.5	3.0	827.0	261.1	1.252
410.6	2.6	1 096.0	334.0	1.549	410.6	2.8	1 052.0	323.0	1.518
492.7	2.5	1 213.0	398.3	1.836	492.7	2.7	1 199.0	383.1	1.832
574.8	2.5	1 252.0	450.9	2.409	574.8	2.6	1 243.0	435.8	2.237
656.9	2.5	1 350.0	500.7	3.037	656.9	2.5	1 296.0	477.3	2.780
$\phi = 0.40$					$\phi = 0.45$				
328.5	3.0	805.0	251.0	1.163	328.5	3.2	778.0	239.4	1.162
410.6	2.9	1 016.0	313.2	1.412	410.6	3.0	940.0	298.0	1.376
492.7	2.8	1 186.0	375.0	1.648	492.7	3.0	1 154.0	358.4	1.641
574.8	2.7	1 230.0	424.1	2.034	574.8	2.9	1 223.5	410.1	1.946
656.9	2.6	1 266.5	464.8	2.497	656.9	2.8	1 253.0	452.5	2.332
$\phi = 0.50$					$\phi = 0.55$				
328.5	3.3	742.0	229.1	1.093	328.5	3.4	730.0	224.7	0.963
410.6	3.2	924.0	290.4	1.282	410.6	3.3	893.5	282.4	1.154
492.7	3.1	1 120.0	348.3	1.492	492.7	3.2	1 104.0	338.5	1.346
574.8	3.0	1 215.0	399.3	1.755	574.8	3.1	1 202.0	387.1	1.587
656.9	2.9	1 246.5	439.9	2.098	656.9	3.0	1 231.1	425.1	1.897
$\phi = 0.60$									
328.5	3.5	694.0	210.3	0.919					
410.6	3.4	839.0	265.2	1.099					
492.7	3.3	1 031.0	317.6	1.284					
574.8	3.2	1 162.0	362.8	1.508					
656.9	3.1	1 219.0	403.1	1.748					

TABLE 4 - ADSORPTION ISOTHERM DATA FOR *p*-XYLENE/WATER EMULSIONS WITH SODIUM OLEATE AS SURFACTANT AT $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$

$C \times 10^4$ mol dm ⁻³	\bar{r} μ	$K_s \times 10^6$ $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$C_s \times 10^4$ mol dm ⁻³	$a \times 10^6$ mol cm ⁻²	$C \times 10^4$ mol dm ⁻³	\bar{r} μ	$K_s \times 10^6$ $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$C_s \times 10^4$ mol dm ⁻³	$a \times 10^6$ mol cm ⁻²
$\phi = 0.30$					$\phi = 0.35$				
328.5	2.8	847.0	268.0	1.318	328.5	3.0	828.0	261.4	1.246
410.6	2.6	1 097.0	334.2	1.545	410.6	2.8	1 053.0	323.3	1.513
492.7	2.5	1 213.0	398.3	1.836	492.7	2.7	1 199.0	381.1	1.832
574.8	2.5	1 251.7	450.5	2.415	574.8	2.6	1 243.5	435.9	2.236
656.9	2.5	1 348.0	500.3	3.045	656.9	2.5	1 298.5	477.6	2.775
$\phi = 0.40$					$\phi = 0.45$				
328.5	3.0	804.0	250.9	1.164	328.5	3.2	777.0	239.0	1.167
410.6	2.9	1 015.0	313.0	1.415	410.6	3.0	938.0	297.7	1.380
492.7	2.8	1 185.0	374.8	1.651	492.7	3.0	1 140.0	358.4	1.641
574.8	2.7	1 230.0	424.1	2.034	574.8	2.9	1 224.0	410.4	1.942
656.9	2.6	1 267.0	465.1	2.493	656.9	2.8	1 255.0	452.8	2.328
$\phi = 0.50$					$\phi = 0.55$				
328.5	3.3	741.0	229.0	1.095	328.5	3.4	729.0	224.6	0.963
410.6	3.2	922.0	290.0	1.286	410.6	3.3	893.0	282.2	1.156
492.7	3.1	1 120.0	348.3	1.492	492.7	3.2	1 105.0	338.7	1.344
574.8	3.0	1 215.0	399.3	1.755	574.8	3.1	1 201.0	386.7	1.590
656.9	2.9	1 247.0	440.3	2.094	656.9	3.0	1 232.0	425.4	1.894
$\phi = 0.60$									
328.5	3.5	693.0	210.1	0.911					
410.6	3.4	839.0	265.2	1.099					
492.7	3.3	1 031.0	317.6	1.284					
574.8	3.2	1 161.0	362.0	1.509					
656.9	3.1	1 219.0	403.1	1.748					

droplet surface in the emulsions does not saturate at $C_s = \text{CMC-III}$ and continues on to some extent even though $C_s > \text{CMC-III}$. This is in conformity with the author's earlier observation¹

in the case of benzene-water-sodium oleate emulsions. The amount a of sodium oleate adsorbed per cm² of the droplet surface corresponding to C_s which is in effect the equilibrium sodium oleate

concentration in the aqueous serum of the emulsions, was calculated in each case by the equation,

$$a = \frac{(1-\phi)(C-C_s)\bar{r}}{3000\phi} \quad (1)$$

where the symbols signify as defined earlier. The values of a as calculated by equation (1) are also incorporated in Tables 1-4.

The $a-C_s$ data were fitted for the Langmuir type adsorption isotherm⁹,

$$\frac{1}{a} = \left(\frac{A}{C_m}\right) \frac{1}{C_s} + \frac{1}{C_m} \quad (2)$$

where, C_m is the surfactant adsorbed (mol cm^{-2}) at the effective monolayer adsorption and is a system constant while A is another constant with the same unit as C_s . The $1/a$ vs $1/C_s$ plots were linear for smaller values of C_s only. One such representative plot for toluene-water-sodium oleate emulsions at 30° with $\phi = 0.45$ is shown in Fig. 1. With C_m as determined from the intercept of

Fig. 1. Plots of $1/a$ vs $1/C_s$ for toluene-water emulsion with sodium oleate as surfactant and $\phi = 0.45$ at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

the linear portion of such plots, the area σ_L occupied by one sodium oleate molecule adsorbed in Langmuir type adsorption monolayer was calculated using the equation,

$$\sigma_L = [N C_m]^{-1} \quad (3)$$

where, N is the Avogadro number. The values of σ_L as calculated in each case (Table 5) are much smaller than $\sim 20 \text{ \AA}^2$ per molecule which is the area occupied¹⁰ by an adsorbed sodium oleate molecule in a packed adsorption monolayer. Thus the nonlinearity of the Langmuir adsorption isotherm and the fact that $\sigma_L < 20 \text{ \AA}^2$ per molecule indicate that the oleate adsorption on drop surface of the emulsions studied is not of monolayer type.

TABLE 5 - VALUES OF σ_L , σ_B AND E_{ad} FOR METHYL-SUBSTITUTED-BENZENE - WATER EMULSIONS WITH SODIUM OLEATE AS SURFACTANT AT $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$

ϕ	σ_L \AA^2 molecule^{-1}	σ_B \AA^2 molecule^{-1}	E_{ad} kcal mol^{-1}
Toluene/Water emulsion			
0.30	1.328	20.3	1.8
0.35	1.625	19.9	1.7
0.40	4.151	20.2	1.6
0.45	4.051	20.1	1.6
0.50	4.068	21.4	1.6
0.55	4.317	22.9	1.7
0.60	4.040	22.2	1.5
			Av. $E_{ad} = 1.6$
<i>o</i> -Xylene/Water emulsion			
0.30	2.283	20.0	1.6
0.35	3.155	19.9	1.7
0.40	4.151	20.7	1.7
0.45	4.499	20.6	1.7
0.50	4.026	19.3	1.8
0.55	4.005	22.5	1.6
0.60	4.051	22.6	1.6
			Av. $E_{ad} = 1.7$
<i>m</i> -Xylene/Water emulsion			
0.30	2.324	20.1	1.5
0.35	2.656	19.9	1.8
0.40	2.532	20.0	1.4
0.45	2.494	20.1	1.5
0.50	3.653	21.4	1.6
0.55	3.487	22.2	1.5
0.60	3.514	21.6	1.4
			Av. $E_{ad} = 1.5$
<i>p</i> -Xylene/Water emulsion			
0.30	2.391	20.0	1.6
0.35	2.684	19.6	1.6
0.40	2.656	20.1	1.5
0.45	2.989	20.1	1.6
0.50	3.181	21.0	1.5
0.55	3.736	21.5	1.3
0.60	4.012	21.1	1.2
			Av. $E_{ad} = 1.5$
Overall Av. (E_{ad})MSB = 1.6			

In order to test whether the oleate adsorption on emulsion droplets is of multilayer type, the BET (Brunauer, Emmet and Teller) adsorption isotherms were plotted according to the following 3-parameter equation¹¹,

$$\frac{C_s}{a(C'_s - C_s)} = \left[\frac{1-K}{a_m}\right] \frac{C_s}{C'_s} + \frac{K}{a_m} \quad (4)$$

where, a_m is the amount of surfactant adsorbed (mol cm^{-2}) for complete monolayer coverage, K is a constant depending on the energy of adsorption and C'_s represents a characteristic value of C_s and is equal to the critical surfactant concentration in the serum for which the saturation surfactant adsorption on drop surface is achieved.

The BET adsorption isotherms as obtained by plotting $C_s/a(C'_s - C_s)$ vs C_s/C'_s with empirically determined value of $C'_s = 0.068 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

for the emulsion systems studied were satisfactorily linear indicating that the oleate adsorption on the emulsion droplets is of multilayer type. One such typical adsorption isotherm for toluene-water-sodium oleate emulsions at 30° with $\phi = 0.45$ is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Plots of $\frac{1}{a} \left[\frac{C_s}{C_s - C_s} \right]$ vs C_s / C_s for toluene-water emulsion with sodium oleate as surfactant and $\phi = 0.45$ at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

It may be pointed out here that such multilayers or the liquid crystalline layers^{1,2} on the drop surface in oil-water emulsion systems are the successive surfactant ion arrays with the hydrophilic head groups pointing towards each other which are separated by squeezed-in aqueous phase having counter ions in it. Such multilayers impart pronounced emulsion stability by checking coalescence as recognised by Friberg *et al.*^{1,2}. As our adsorption data have been collected for creamed emulsions with C_s in the post-micellar range, the existence of similar type of adsorbed oleate multilayers on the drop surface is obvious.

Using the slope and the corresponding intercept of the linear BET isotherms, a_m and K were determined in each case. The values of a_m were utilised to calculate the area σ_B occupied by a sodium oleate molecule on the droplet surface for BET-type multilayer adsorption by the equation,

$$\sigma_B = [N a_m]^{-1} \quad (5)$$

while the values of K were used to calculate the molar energy of adsorption (E_{ad}) by the equation^{1,2},

$$K = e^{-E_{ad}/RT} \quad (6)$$

where, R is the molar gas constant and T the temperature. It may be pointed out here that $E_{ad} =$

$(\psi - \lambda)$, where ψ is the energy required to remove one adsorbed molecule from otherwise free adsorbent surface and λ the latent heat of vaporisation per molecule of adsorbate.

A perusal of the calculated values of σ_B (Table 5) shows that they do not vary significantly with ϕ or with the nature of the disperse phase used and the overall average surface area per adsorbed sodium oleate molecule $\bar{\sigma}_B$ equals $20.8 \pm 0.9 \text{ \AA}^2$ per molecule which compares quite satisfactorily with the area 20.5 \AA^2 per molecule occupied in tightly packed condensed film of sodium oleate formed on air-water interface. This suggests that the adsorbed surfactant ions in the first layer on the drop surface in all the emulsions studied are tightly packed with their hydrophobic surfactant tails attached to the drops and the corresponding hydrophilic polar heads pointing out towards the aqueous medium.

Further, the reported values of E_{ad} (Table 5) which are less than 2 kcal in each case, do not vary significantly with ϕ for the same emulsion system and show an uncertainty in their determination not exceeding ± 0.2 kcal mol⁻¹. The E_{ad} values of this order rule out the possibility of chemisorption and implies that the adsorption of sodium oleate at the drop surface in these systems is the outcome of the hydrophobic interaction involving forces of lesser magnitude. The average E_{ad} for the emulsions of toluene, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-xylene are 1.6, 1.7, 1.5 and 1.5 kcal respectively, with an overall average $(\bar{E}_{ad})_{MSB}$ for all the methyl-substituted-benzenes equal to 1.6 kcal (Table 5) indicating that the adsorption sites on the drop surface in each case are similar in nature.

With methyl-substituted-benzenes as disperse phase in oil-water-sodium oleate emulsions, the adsorption sites may comprise of either =CH or CH₃ groups of the adjacent molecules in the drop surface. In case the adsorption sites are formed of =CH group, the value of $(\bar{E}_{ad})_{MSB}$ would have been either equal to or higher than the average adsorption energy $(\bar{E}_{ad})_B$ for oleate ions as adsorbate and benzene as disperse phase because =CH groups in methyl-substituted-benzenes are either similar or more active than =CH groups in benzene due to inductive and hyperconjugation effect of the methyl groups as substituents in the benzene ring of the former. But as reported earlier¹ the value of $(\bar{E}_{ad})_B$ is 2.3 kcal which is significantly higher than $(\bar{E}_{ad})_{MSB} = 1.6$ kcal (Table 5). This leads to the conclusion that the adsorption sites in the methyl-substituted-benzenes are different and less active than those in the benzene emulsions and are consequently formed of CH₃ groups. Accordingly, in methyl-substituted-benzene emulsions studied, the adsorption results with the interaction between CH₃ group of methyl-substituted-benzenes as adsorption sites in the drop surface with terminal CH₃ group of oleate ions as

adsorbate. Such $(-CH_3)_{drop}$ $(-CH_3)_{oleate}$ adsorption is facilitated in comparison to similar $(=CH)_{drop}$ $(-CH_3)_{oleate}$ adsorption possibly because of the preferred steric as well as hydrophobic effects. In view of the fact that $=CH$ group of benzene is more active due to the existence of π -electrons in comparison to the CH_3 group of the methyl-substituted-benzenes, the lower value $(\bar{E}_{ad})_{MSB}$ than $(\bar{E}_{ad})_B$ is also obvious.

It may be pointed out here that in most cases of solid - gas and solid - liquid adsorption studies where BET equation is generally applicable, the adsorption sites and the solid adsorbent molecules forming such sites are fixed. In case of liquid adsorbents also, the site remains fixed even though the liquid molecules constituting such sites may be mobile. Once the molecules get adsorbed, the liquid molecules constituting the adsorption sites become immobile and the situation becomes similar to those as encountered in the case of solid - gas or solid - liquid adsorption. Moreover, once the first adsorbed layer becomes compact, the emulsified droplets act like solid adsorbents for further multilayer adsorption. Thus for the applicability of BET equation, no assumption made in its derivation is significantly violated by the systems studied.

Assuming the radial approach of oncoming surfactant ions for layer formation on drop surface¹, the number of surfactant layers (ν) on the drop surface in case of each emulsion was calculated using the equation¹,

$$\nu = \frac{N \bar{r} \sigma_B (1 - \phi) (C - C_s)}{3000 \phi} \quad (7)$$

The values of ν for different emulsions with $210.0 \times 10^{-4} < C_s < C'_s$ are given in Table 6 which shows that ν in all cases is more than 1 and varies with ϕ for constant C and vice versa. The maximum number of adsorbed layers ν_{max} for each emulsion with $C_s = C'_s$ was calculated by modifying equation (7) in the following form¹,

$$\nu_{max} = \frac{N \bar{r}' \sigma_B (1 - \phi) (C' - C'_s)}{3000 \phi} \quad (8)$$

where, \bar{r}' and C' are the values of \bar{r} and C corresponding to $C_s = C'_s$ and were obtained by extrapolation of \bar{r} vs C/ϕ and C vs C_s curves respectively for each ϕ . The extrapolated value of \bar{r}' was found to be 2.5μ for each ϕ and for every emulsion, while the extrapolated values of C' varied with ϕ and the emulsion system. The values of ν_{max} (Table 6) as

TABLE 6 - VALUES OF ν AND ν_{max} FOR METHYL-SUBSTITUTED-BENZENE - WATER EMULSIONS WITH SODIUM OLEATE AS SURFACTANT AT $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$

ϕ	ν					ν_{max}
	$C = 0.03285$ mol dm ⁻³	$C = 0.04106$ mol dm ⁻³	$C = 0.04927$ mol dm ⁻³	$C = 0.05748$ mol dm ⁻³	$C = 0.06569$ mol dm ⁻³	
Toluene/Water emulsion						
0.30	1.544	1.882	2.223	2.941	3.714	3.733
0.35	1.482	1.814	2.178	2.676	3.331	3.339
0.40	1.487	1.718	1.996	2.478	3.051	3.650
0.45	1.461	1.572	1.981	2.367	2.836	3.366
0.50	1.389	1.565	1.923	2.256	2.696	3.169
0.55	1.328	1.558	1.884	2.193	2.616	3.009
0.60	1.225	1.469	1.714	2.011	2.338	3.157
o-Xylene/Water emulsion						
0.30	1.498	1.861	2.202	2.923	3.675	3.698
0.35	1.491	1.820	2.196	2.689	3.339	3.339
0.40	1.446	1.759	2.054	2.550	3.138	3.117
0.45	1.436	1.708	2.040	2.429	2.916	3.033
0.50	1.418	1.655	1.926	2.386	2.706	3.204
0.55	1.308	1.566	1.858	2.155	2.578	3.142
0.60	1.255	1.497	1.749	2.054	2.386	3.100
m-Xylene/Water emulsion						
0.30	1.542	1.875	2.222	2.917	3.677	3.649
0.35	1.500	1.819	2.196	2.681	3.331	3.617
0.40	1.400	1.701	1.984	2.451	3.008	3.840
0.45	1.399	1.657	1.977	2.344	2.808	3.349
0.50	1.409	1.653	1.923	2.262	2.704	3.437
0.55	1.286	1.542	1.791	2.121	2.536	3.373
0.60	1.196	1.429	1.671	1.961	2.275	3.231
p-Xylene/Water emulsion						
0.30	1.587	1.861	2.211	2.911	3.668	3.747
0.35	1.471	1.786	2.163	2.639	3.276	3.563
0.40	1.409	1.713	1.998	2.463	3.019	3.783
0.45	1.413	1.671	1.987	2.351	2.819	3.453
0.50	1.384	1.627	1.887	2.220	2.648	3.478
0.55	1.248	1.496	1.740	2.059	2.453	3.178
0.60	1.170	1.396	1.632	1.918	2.222	3.318

calculated by equation (8) are in the range $3 < \nu_{\max} < 4$ which shows that the number of completely formed layers is 3. This supports the earlier contention² that the most probable value of the maximum number of completely adsorbed layers in oil-water emulsions with anionic surfactants should be an odd number.

With maximum number of completely adsorbed layers equal to 3, the total film thickness (l_T) for oleate as the surfactant ion in methyl-substituted-benzene-water-sodium oleate emulsions was calculated by the equation²,

$$l_T = (l_{\text{COO}^-} + l_{\text{C-O}}) + (\nu_{\max} - 1) [l_{\text{COO}^-} + l_{\text{HO}} + \frac{1}{2}(l_p + l_h)] \quad (9)$$

where, $l_{\text{COO}^-} = l_{\text{C-O}} \cos \theta/2$ and

$$l_{\text{HO}} = 16 l_{\text{C-O}} + l_{\text{OH}_2} + l_{\text{C-O}}$$

where, $l_{\text{C-O}}$ is the C-O bond length, θ the $\text{C} \leq \text{O}^-$ bond angle, $l_{\text{C-C}}$ the C-C bond length, $l_{\text{C=O}}$ the C=C bond length, l_{OH_2} the projection of the C-H bond on the axis of the hydrocarbon chain, l_p the distance between the two polar heads and l_h the distance between the two hydrocarbon chains of a bilayer. Using the standard values of bond lengths¹⁴ along with $\theta = 124.5^\circ$, $l_p = 20 \text{ \AA}$ and $l_h \sim 5 \text{ \AA}$, the value of l_T is found to be $\sim 83 \text{ \AA}$. The calculated value of l_T for benzene-water-sodium oleate emulsions as reported² earlier was also equal to 83 \AA . This leads to the conclusion that the methyl substitution in benzene as disperse phase

does not change the surfactant film thickness in corresponding emulsions with water as dispersing phase and sodium oleate as surfactant.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (N.N.P.) is thankful to Professor K. D. Banerji, Head of the Department of Chemistry, Bhagalpur University, for facilities.

References

1. S. S. SINGH, N. N. PANDEY and R. P. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1988, 27, 104.
2. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text-book of Practical Organic Chemistry", Longmans Green, London, 1968, p. 173.
3. S. S. SINGH, Ph.D. Thesis, Bhagalpur University, 1975.
4. J. TIMMERMANS, "Physicochemical Constants of Pure Organic Compounds", Elsevier, New York, 1950, p. 161.
5. A. FINDLAY, "Practical Physical Chemistry", 8th. ed., Longmans Green, London, 1965, p. 206.
6. L. I. OSIPOW, "Surface Chemistry: Theory and Industrial Applications", Reinhold, New York, 1964, p. 186.
7. P. H. ELWORTHY, A. T. FLORENCE and C. B. MACFARLANE, "Solubilization by Surface Active Agents", Chapman and Hall, London, 1968, p. 30.
8. Y. ZIMMELS and I. LIN, *Colloid Polym. Sci.*, 1974, 252, 597.
9. M. J. ROSEN, "Surfactants and Interfacial Phenomena", Wiley, New York, 1978, p. 37.
10. N. K. ADAM, *Nature (London)*, 1957, 180, 50.
11. T. GU, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 1982, 85, 602.
12. S. FRIBERG, P. O. JANSSON and E. CEDERBERG, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 1976, 55, 614.
13. E. A. MOELWYN-HUGHES, "Physical Chemistry", Pergamon, London, 1961, p. 968.
14. C. N. R. RAO, M. V. GEORGE and J. MAHANTY, "A Handbook of Chemistry and Physics", Affiliated East West Press, New Delhi, 1970, p. 227.